

**STUDY OF SELF-EVALUATION GRADING AND RANKING METHOD BY B.Ed.
TRAINEE ON MICROTEACHING LESSON SKILLS**

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Abstract

Investment in teacher education can yield very rich dividends, because the financial resource required a small when measured against the resulting improvements, in the education of millions. First rate teacher training institutions thus play a crucial role in the development of education. After completing teaching-learning process, to measure the achievement of the objectives teacher uses various kind different kind of evaluation system. Microteaching is the platform of teacher-students for the all kind of practice teaching. During this situation supervisor and teacher-students interact. In this present study total 87 teacher-students were selected randomly during the year of 2008-2009 from the Swami Vivekanand Sarvoday Education college Mehsana. Students were informed about self evaluation method. Teach and re-teach system organize and self-evaluation method employed for the present study. The former needs of microteaching to communicate his/her feelings, impression and various views of matter. From the research it has found that introduction, explanation and using black board work skill found significant in the re-teach.

Key words: Self-Evaluation, Grading and Ranking Method, B.Ed. Trainee, Microteaching Lesson, Skills

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Nagalpur Mehsana,
Gujaratdesire4sureshparmar@gmail.com**Introduction**

Investment in teacher education can yield very rich dividends, because the financial resource required is small when measured against the resulting improvements in the education of millions. First rate teacher training institutions thus play a crucial role in the development of education." Indeed the Kothari commission has given importance to the role of teacher education. Education is the bipolar process in the context of classroom, there is one pole is teacher and another is student. Concept of the microteaching had first developed in 1961 in California University. Prof. Divite Alane had used first time the word of 'microteaching' and developed Micro-clinic in 1964-65. After work on microteaching it had said that microteaching is not the process of teaching, but it is the process to get the skill. Now, the training of the teacher microteaching becomes the technique of make a teacher to skillful. In the history of MT Center of the Advanced Study in Education (CASE) of the M.S. University, Baroda had started at practical base in Punjab for two years. After 1976 it is applied to the University of the County for the part of teacher training. The former needs of microteaching to communicate his/her feelings, impression and various views of matter. To provide the scope of improvement supervisor and observer shares the perception about the teacher-student's achievements. In this study researcher tries to focus on that in microteaching teacher-student try to get the various skills of teaching. In this process teacher-student evaluate him by the self-evaluation for further improvements.

PROBLEM OF THE STUDY**STUDY OF SELF-EVALUATION GRADING AND RANKING METHOD BY B.Ed.
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OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the study of self-evaluation of grade of skill of microteaching and rank of the skill of the microteaching of trainee of B. Ed faculty.
2. To study the study of self-evaluation of grade of skill of microteaching and rank of the skill of the microteaching of male trainee of B. Ed faculty.
3. To study the study of self-evaluation of grade of skill of microteaching and rank of the skill of the microteaching of female trainee of B. Ed faculty.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

1. There will be no significant difference between mean score of introduction grade and mean score of introduction rank of self-evaluation of trainee.
2. There will be no significant difference between mean score of question grade and mean score of question rank of self-evaluation of trainee.
3. There will be no significant difference between mean score of reinforcement grade and mean score of question rank of self-evaluation of trainee.
4. There will be no significant difference between mean score of illustration grade and mean score of illustration rank of self-evaluation of trainee.
5. There will be no significant difference between mean score of explaining grade and mean score of explaining rank of self-evaluation of trainee.
6. There will be no significant difference between mean score of black-board work grade and mean score of black-board work rank of self-evaluation of trainee.
7. There will be no significant difference between mean score of introduction grade and mean score of introduction rank of self-evaluation of male trainee.
8. There will be no significant difference between mean score of question grade and mean score of question rank of self-evaluation of male trainee.
9. There will be no significant difference between mean score of reinforcement grade and mean score of question rank of self-evaluation of male trainee.
10. There will be no significant difference between mean score of illustration grade and mean score of illustration rank of self-evaluation of male trainee.
11. There will be no significant difference between mean score of explaining grade and mean score of explaining rank of self-evaluation of male trainee.
12. There will be no significant difference between mean score of black-board work grade and mean score of black-board work rank of self-evaluation of male trainee.

13. There will be no significant difference between mean score of introduction grade and mean score of introduction rank of self-evaluation of female trainee.
14. There will be no significant difference between mean score of question grade and mean score of question rank of self-evaluation of female trainee.
15. There will be no significant difference between mean score of reinforcement grade and mean score of question rank of self-evaluation of female trainee.
16. There will be no significant difference between mean score of illustration grade and mean score of illustration rank of self-evaluation of female trainee.
17. There will be no significant difference between mean score of explaining grade and mean score of explaining rank of self-evaluation of female trainee.
18. There will be no significant difference between mean score of black-board work grade and mean score of black-board work rank of self-evaluation of female trainee.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The present study is casual comparative study and according the methodology was used. Data regarding the grade and rank of the skill of the microteaching collected from the trainee by using questionnaire, Whereas, the data regarding different variable were collected directly from the trainee.

POPULATION STUDY

All the B.Ed, trainee of the of the colleges affiliated to H.N.G.U were population of the study during the year of 2018-2019.

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

All the B.Ed, trainee of the of the 4 affiliated to H.N.G.U selected and finally 73 female and 36 male trainee were selected as the sample for the present study.

TOOLS USED FOR THE STUDY

For the present study all the B.Ed, trainee of the college were instructed for grade and rank of the microteaching by self-evaluation, There are six type of the microteaching skill were used those are Introduction of the lesson, Questioning, Reinforcement, Illustration with Example, explaining and using Black-board. Grade had dividing in five parts for each skill of microteaching. (Performance of 80 to 100 for A-Grade, 60 to 79 for

B-Grade, 40 to 159 for C-Grade, 20 to 39 for D-Grade, 00 to 19 for E-Grade). 5 marks given to A-Grade, 4 marks given to B-Grade, 3 marks given to C-Grade, 2 marks given to D-Grade, 1 marks given to E-Grade. Same type of the Rank system trainee have to give 1 to 6 rank for above six skill of the micro teaching according to their choice according to their command over the skill. 1 rank have given 6 marks, 2 rank have given 5 marks, 3 rank have given 4 marks, 4 rank have given 3 marks, 5 rank have given 2 marks, 6 rank have given 1 marks, Questionnaire was given to the trainee to fill grade and rank of each skill according to their choice by self-evaluation.

DATA COLLECTION

For the collection of data, questionnaire containing grade and rank for each micro-teaching six skill for self-evaluation given to the 73 female and 36 male trainee were after completing micro-teaching lesson.

DATA ANALYSIS

As it is comparative study, descriptive statistics did the data analysis for the present study. The descriptive statistical technique like mean, standard deviation, and t-test were used in data analysis.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY AND TABLE:

TABLE – 1
(Grade and Rank of Male Trainee)

Variables	t-Value	Significance
INT_1_/INT_2_	1.35	Significant
QUE_1_/QUE_2_	1.31	No Significant
REL_1_/REL_2_	0.63	No Significant
EXA_1_/EXA_2_	1.63	No Significant
EXP_1_/EXP_2_	5.42	Significant
BBV_1_/BBV_2_	1.72	Significant

TABLE – 2
(Grade and Rank of Female Trainee)

<u>Variables</u>	t-Value	Significance
INT_1_/INT_2_	2.69	Significant
QUE_1_/QUE_2_	1.98	No Significant
REL_1_/REL_2_	0.45	No Significant
EXA_1_/EXA_2_	2.45	No Significant
EXP_1_/EXP_2_	2.36	Significant
BBV_1_/BBV_2_	3.24	Significant

TABLE –3
(Grade and Rank of Total Trainee)

<u>Variables</u>	t-Value	Significance
INT_1_/INT_2_	2.91	Significant
QUE_1_/QUE_2_	1.84	No Significant
REL_1_/REL_2_	0.58	No Significant
EXA_1_/EXA_2_	1.06	No Significant
EXP_1_/EXP_2_	5.43	Significant
BBV_1_/BBV_2_	3.807	Significant

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION OF THE STUDY

From the above table it can be different said that -

- There is significations found in the mean score of grade is higher than mean score of rank of self-evaluation of all trainee and female only for introduction skill, male trainee's score has no significant difference.

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- There is no any significant difference found in mean score of grade and rank of self-evaluation of question and reinforcement skill for all, male and female trainee.
- Significant difference difference has found in the mean score of grade is higher than mean score of rank of self-evaluation of female trainee for illustration with example skill, all trainee and male trainee's score has no significant difference.
- It is noted that Significant difference /found for explaining skill. Significant difference has found in the mean score of rank is higher than mean score of grade of self-evaluation of all trainee and male only for explaining skill, and significant difference has found in the mean score of grade is higher than mean score of rank of self-evaluation of all trainee and female only for explaining skill.
- Significant difference found in the mean score of rank is higher than mean score of grade of self-evaluation of all trainee and male only for using black-board skill, female trainee's score has no significant difference.

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